

Research Article

Variability in Human Lives: Biological Determinism in Reproductive Health Research

Marco Rocchetti

Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, Italy

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

Mura A. Zamboni 7, 40126 Bologna, Italy

marco.rocchetti@unibo.it - ORCID: 0000-0003-1264-8595

Authors contributions: MR was the sole author of the manuscript. Conceptualization, M. R.; methodology, M. R.; validation, M. R.; formal analysis, M.R.; investigation, M. R.; resources, M. R.; data curation, M.R.; writing – original draft preparation, M.R.; writing – review and editing, M.R.; visualization, M. R.; supervision, M.R.; project administration, M.R.; funding acquisition, M. R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgements: Not applicable

Funding: Not applicable

Abstract

Background: Modern epigenetics increasingly employs biological clocks to quantify the impact of life choices on aging. Recent high-impact studies have claimed that childbearing significantly accelerates biological aging in women. This article critically re-examines these claims, challenging the growing trend of biological determinism imposed on reproductive choices through large-scale genomic datasets.

Methods: A rigorous secondary analysis was performed on demographic and epigenetic data from recent influential research. The study utilizes Fisher's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to partition variance and Cohen's d to calculate standardized effect sizes. The goal was to quantify the actual predictive power of reproductive history on female lifespan and biological destiny compared to stochastic and genetic factors.

Results: The analysis reveals that while reproductive history may reach statistical significance in large samples, its explanatory power is negligible, accounting for only 1.2% of the variance in female lifespan. Conversely, 98.8% of biological aging remains governed by stochastic noise and genetics. With a standardized effect size near zero ($d = 0.11$) and a survival distribution overlap of 95.6% between groups, the epigenetic signals attributed to childbearing are shown to be biologically and practically irrelevant.

Conclusions: The obsession with microscopic p-values in massive datasets distorts scientific reality and creates unjustified societal anxiety. This work demonstrates that current epigenetic signals

provide no reliable basis for life-altering labels or reproductive penalties. The study calls for a return to scientific realism, distinguishing between molecular *non sequiturs* and tangible health outcomes, ultimately defending the stochastic freedom of human life.

Keywords: Epigenetic, Biological determinism, Variance partitioning, Reproductive health, Effect size

1. Introduction

Modern epigenetics increasingly relies on biological clocks to quantify the impact of life choices on human aging. While these advancements hold promise, a problematic trend has emerged: the tendency to leverage large-scale genomic datasets to assign biological penalties or rewards to individual reproductive choices. This article critically re-examines the statistical foundation of this growing determinism, arguing that current interpretations often conflate mathematical significance with clinical or biological reality.

As researchers in the field of medical data analysis, we maintain that scientific integrity requires a rigorous distinction between a statistically detectable signal in a large cohort and a meaningful outcome for the individual. We contend that the current focus on microscopic p-values in massive datasets, a phenomenon we term manufacturing ghosts, distorts the scientific landscape. By re-analyzing the variance explained by reproductive history in current high-impact literature, this study demonstrates that these claims often lack the effect size necessary to support the deterministic

narratives currently being constructed. The objective is not to challenge the molecular data itself, but to demonstrate that when the *effect size* [1] is submerged by the background stochastic noise of human vital dynamics, the resulting labels attached to reproductive choices are mathematically questionable.

In fact, a fundamental contradiction plagues modern high-impact publishing. In editorial discussions, it is often acknowledged that such studies aim to analyze the specific contribution of life events to lifespan. However, our analysis will prove precisely that this contribution is statistically indistinguishable from zero in any practical or biological sense.

Simply put, authors of study [2] have suggested that women not having children may undergo an accelerated biological aging of about 1.0 year. Instead we say that to speak of a meaningful contribution when the individual risk is effectively a 53.1% coin toss (as I am going to demonstrate) should be considered just nonsensical. To be further clear: a 1.2% of women's life variance (explained with reproductive history as we will show) means that for every 100 days of difference in lifespan, 99 days are determined by everything else, genetics, environment, choices or simple luck, and only one day is linked to the factor in question. To build a public health narrative, or worse, a moral one, on such a microscopic sliver of data is not just an exaggeration; it is again a mathematical non-sense that ignores the overwhelming 98.8% prevalence of human reality.

For example, would any of us invest our life's savings based on information that covers only 1% of the total risk? Certainly not, I hope. Why, then, do we allow such an investment of anxiety in women's lives based on the same microscopic probability?

2. Data and Methods

Before discussing the data and the main methods employed to analyze the findings exposed in [2], we must first acknowledge a fundamental mechanic of modern biostatistics: with a large enough sample size (n), even the smallest biological signal can reach high statistical significance ($p < 0.0001$), the holy grail of modern research. For instance, to promote a clinically minor shift of 6 months ($\Delta = 0.5$) to a highly significant discovery in a population with a standard deviation of 9.1 years (σ), a sample of approximately 10,000 subjects is sufficient, as shown in the equation developed below:

$$n = (3.89 \times 9.1 / 0.5)^2 \cong 5,012 \text{ subjects per group} . \quad (1)$$

Obviously, to achieve the result above we have reasonably assumed that mortality within a specific age-window (50–70 years) can be locally approximated as a homoscedastic Normal distribution, where any biological shift Δ acts as a linear displacement of the mean without deforming the population variance σ^2 [2].

But the real problem is that, while these results are statistically valid and potentially interesting for future longitudinal research, they often lack immediate clinical weight for the individual patient as we will explain in a while. While we confirm to remain open to the possibility that epigenetic shifts are precursors to future health trends, however we posit that these signals must be anchored in a broader demographic context.

Thus, we come back to [2] and use data from the Italian Institute for Statistics (ISTAT, years 2023–2024) [3] as a robust proxy for high-longevity European female populations. In particular, using that

data, we can observe a standard deviation (σ) in survival of 9.1 years for women at age of 50 (ISTAT 2026). It should be noticed that demographic and mortality data used in this study are publicly available from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) at:

https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/it/dw/categories/IT1,POP,1.0/POP_MORTALITY/DCIS_MORTALITA1/IT1,26_295_DF_DCIS_MORTALITA1_1,1.0 . (also referenced as [3] in this

manuscript). The specific datasets used are the 'Tavole di mortalità della popolazione residente' (2023-2024). All mathematical derivations and statistical calculations performed on these public data are fully described within the manuscript to ensure reproducibility.

Coming now to the methodologies employed to use those data, this study develops a quantitative secondary analysis to evaluate the biological relevance of epigenetic aging signals reported in [2]. To distinguish between statistical significance and scientific realism, the following mathematical framework was applied as based on the use of the following techniques.

First we used Fisher's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and variance partitioning [4]. The study utilizes the principle of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), as pioneered by R.A. Fisher, to partition the total observed variability in female lifespan. By comparing the squared biological shift (Δ^2), attributed to reproductive history, against the total population variance (σ^2), we calculated the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). This metric quantifies the exact percentage of life expectancy variance that can be explained by the reproductive factor, effectively separating the signal from the overwhelming stochastic noise of human vital dynamics.

Then, to assess the magnitude of the epigenetic effect independently of the sample size we adopted the standardized effect size calculating the Cohen's d coefficient [5]. Unlike p-values, which only indicate the likelihood that an effect exists, the effect size measures its practical weight. A Cohen's d is computed as the ratio of the difference between means (Δ) to the standard deviation (σ). This allows us to determine if the reported biological aging acceleration is a large effect or, as in this case, a negligible one that remains submerged within natural population variability.

Not only that, but to translate abstract statistical figures into tangible risks, we resorted to the use of Z-score and Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) first converting the effect size into a Z-score [6]. The Z-score represents the distance between two individuals (e.g., nulliparous vs. others) in terms of standard deviations. Instead, by applying the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF), denoted as $\Phi(z)$, we calculated the actual probability (P) that an individual from one group will experience a shorter lifespan than an individual from the other. This transformation turns a statistically significant finding into a practical probability of outcome, comparable to a coin toss [6].

Finally, we calculated the so-called Overlapping Coefficient (OVL) to visualize the similarity between population distributions. The OVL measures the area shared by two probability density functions. A high OVL (near 100%) indicates that, despite a statistically detectable difference in means, the two groups are functionally and biologically identical for the vast majority of the population. This metric serves as a final check against the distortions of large-sample p-hacking, ensuring that scientific conclusions remain anchored in observable reality [6].

3. Results

After introducing all the methods above, we applied a simplified, yet correct, Fisher's Analysis of Variance, and we got:

$$\text{Variance} = R^2 = \frac{\Delta^2}{\sigma^2} = 1 / 82.81 \cong 0.012 = 1,2\% . \quad (2)$$

This means that reproductive history explains only 1.2% of the variance of life expectancy for the female population (at least using the Italian data). This implies that for an individual (Italian) woman, 98.8% of her biological destiny remains governed by factors far more influential than her reproductive history. While this 1% may be a valuable seed for future biological theories, it remains a whisper amidst the 98.8% amplitude of genetics, lifestyle, and stochastic factors that truly define a woman's lifespan.

If we have not been enough clear in the attempt to motivate whether that 1.0 year of aging really matters or not, we can show the results of the calculation of the so-called standardized effect size (Cohen's d coefficient) [5]. This coefficient tells us how much the signal (Δ) weighs against the noise of natural human variation (σ):

$$d = \frac{\Delta}{\sigma} = 1 / 9.1 \cong 0.112. \quad (3)$$

In biostatistics, a Cohen's d coefficient of 0.11 is considered negligible. It means that the effect is so small that it is completely submerged by the 9.1-year standard deviation found in the robust demographic data of above.

Proceeding with relevant results, if a woman were to ask: "Will not having children shorten my life?", we would feel the duty to understand that she is asking me for a practical probability. Hence, even accepting the linear assumptions of [2] and a standard Normal Distribution, we could try to give a practical answer by transforming the effect size into a Z -score (the standard score that measures the distance between two individuals) and then into a probability using the Cumulative Distribution Function (Φ) by means of the two following equations:

$$z = \frac{\Delta}{\sigma \sqrt{2}} = d / \sqrt{2} \cong 0.11 / 1.41 \cong 0.077, \quad (4)$$

$$P = \Phi(z) = \Phi(0.077) \cong 53.1\%. \quad (5)$$

We got the answer now. If a woman chooses not having children the probability of living a 1 year less is 53.1%, that is a random coin toss. In other words, while the 1.0-year signal produced in [2] is statistically significant, its clinical impact (d) is near zero. Therefore, today the result coming from [2] does not still provide any reliable basis for a life-altering personal advice.

I closing, we feel also the duty to say that a 1-year acceleration in epigenetic aging does not necessarily translate into a 1:1 proportional reduction in actual chronological lifespan. Nonetheless, our analysis remains robust, precisely because it has evaluated that epigenetic signal against the maximum possible resolution of human mortality variance.

By demonstrating that even a literal 1-year shift in life expectancy would be submerged by the stochastic noise of high-longevity populations, we can finally maintain that any subtler or non-linear biological effect would, *a fortiori*, be even more indistinguishable from the background variance of human vital dynamics.

This is further highlighted by computing the so called coefficient of overlapping (OVL) between two groups (nulliparous vs. others) whose computation indicates that the survival trajectories of women with two/three children and without children are 95.6% identical:

$$OVL = 2\Phi\left(-\frac{|d|}{2}\right) \cong 2\Phi(-0.055) \cong 95.6\% . \quad (6)$$

This is graphically visualized by the Figure 1 below:

Figure 1

4. Discussion

We must be brutally clear: the issue here is not a pedantic debate over whether the epigenetic links discussed in [2] are causal. Quite frankly, causality is irrelevant if the magnitude of the effect is invisible to the naked eye of reality. Whether the link is causal or merely associative, our analysis demonstrates that it explains only 1.2% of the variance in survival, leaving a 95.6% overlap between the two groups of women with different reproductive histories. To use such a microscopic sliver of

data to construct a narrative about women's aging is not just a statistical error; it is a failure of scientific integrity.

The modern obsession with finding significance at all costs, the so-called practice of p-hacking, has created a science that is technically significant but practically elusive. By choosing to prioritize p-values over the actual magnitude of the effect, modern science suggest that a molecular non-sense is more important than the tangible complexity of a woman's life. When we interrogate large datasets ($n > 10,000$) until they confess a p-value of 0.0001 for a 1% effect, we are not discovering truth; we are manufacturing ghosts.

As scientists who have seen the evolution of these methods, we have again to state the obvious: Stop p-hacking (women's) science. We cannot allow biostatistics to become a tool for a new form of biological determinism. Science should not be used to label women's reproductive choices with unjustified warnings of accelerated decay when the individual risk remains a 53.1% coin toss. A 1.0-year shift in life expectancy is a signal that is fundamentally submerged by the stochastic noise of high-longevity populations; it is indistinguishable from the background variance of human vital dynamics [7, 8].

It is time for the scientific community to distinguish between a molecular non sequitur and a tangible, life-changing reality. Science should not be a mechanism for imposing biological penalties on the freedom of human choice; it should be a tool for measuring the world as it truly is: vast, varied, complex (and largely beyond the reach of a 1.2% explained variance).

We close calling for a balanced dialogue: one that celebrates molecular progress without sacrificing the autonomy of the individual at the altar of statistical insignificance. Let us stop using p-values to decorate irrelevant findings and start respecting the vast, stochastic freedom that defines the human experience. Science is at its best when it acknowledges its limits, rather than pretending that every fluctuation is a mandate for how a human being should live

5. Conclusion

This article challenges the growing trend of using epigenetic clocks to impose biological determinism on women's reproductive choices. Through a rigorous re-examination of recent high-impact research claiming that childbearing accelerates biological aging, we demonstrate that such findings, while statistically significant, are practically and biologically irrelevant. By applying Fisher's Analysis of Variance and Cohen's effect size to demographic data, we show that reproductive history explains a mere 1.2% of the variance in female lifespan, leaving 98.8% of a woman's biological destiny governed by stochastic noise and genetics.

Limitations to our study need also to be recognized. First, our analysis has locally approximated survival within a specific age window (50–70 years) as a homoscedastic Normal distribution. While human mortality across the entire lifespan follows more complex patterns (e.g., Gompertz-Makeham dynamics), a linear displacement of the mean remains a mathematically robust proxy for evaluating effect sizes in high-longevity cohorts. However, we acknowledge that more sophisticated non-linear

models could further refine the interaction between epigenetic aging and actual chronological survival.

Second, we used demographic data from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) as a proxy for high-longevity European female populations. While Italian women share similar life expectancy and socio-economic profiles with other Western European cohorts, slight variations in environmental or genetic backgrounds across different nations could marginally shift the total variance (σ^2).

Nevertheless, the magnitude of the stochastic noise is so dominant in all modern developed societies that the core conclusion, the negligible impact of reproductive history, remains globally applicable.

Third and conclusive, this study operates on the reported acceleration of epigenetic clocks. It must be noted that a 1.0-year shift in a molecular biomarker does not always translate into a 1:1 reduction in actual lifespan. By treating the epigenetic signal as a direct proxy for survival, our analysis actually grants the original determinist claims the best-case scenario. If the link between these molecular signals and tangible mortality is non-linear or attenuated, the actual explained variance would be even lower than the 1.2% reported here, further confirming the manufacturing of ghosts through p-hacking.

Statements and Declarations:

Data availability

Data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and from the cited References [2, 3]. It should be noticed that demographic and mortality Italian data used in this study as a proxy are publicly available from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) at: https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/it/dw/categories/IT1,POP,1.0/POP_MORTALITY/DCIS_MORTALITA1/IT1,26_295_DF_DCIS_MORTALITA1_1,1.0 . (also referenced as [3] in this manuscript). The specific datasets used are the 'Tavole di mortalità della popolazione residente' (2023-2024). All mathematical derivations and statistical calculations performed on these public data are fully described within the manuscript to ensure reproducibility.

Competing interests

The Author declares no financial or non-financial support to this study.

Authorship

M.R. is the sole author of this work. He conceived the study, developed the mathematical framework, performed the statistical analysis using the ISTAT data proxy, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Ethics Approval

No humans, animals and private data are involved in this study, therefore ethical permission is not required.

Use of AI

The author declares no use of AI.

Funding: Not applicable

References

[1] Grissom RJ, Kim JJ. (2012). *Effect Sizes for Research: Univariate and Multivariate Applications*.

2nd ed. New York: Routledge. ISBN 9780415877695.

[2] Hukkanen M, Kankaanpää A, Heikkinen A, et al. (2026). “Epigenetic Aging and Lifespan Reflect Reproductive History in the Finnish Twin Cohort.” *Nat Comm* 17(70). DOI: 10.1038/s41467-025-67798-y.

[3] ISTAT (Istituto Nazionale di Statistica). (2026). “Life Expectancy Female Population in Italy 2023–2024”. [Accessed 2026 April 20]. Available from:

https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/it/dw/categories/IT1,POP,1.0/POP_MORTALITY/DCIS_MORTALITA1/IT1,26_295_DF_DCIS_MORTALITA1_1,1.0

[4] Fisher RA. (1992). “Statistical Methods for Research Workers” In: *Breakthroughs in Statistics*, Edited by Samuel Kotz and Norman L. Johnson, 66–70. Springer Series in Statistics. New York: Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4612-4380-9_6

[5] Cohen J. (1988). "Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences". 2nd ed. New York: Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9780203771587

[6] Inman HF, Bradley Jr EL. (1989). "The overlapping coefficient as a measure of agreement between probability distributions and point estimation of the overlap of two normal densities". *Commun Stat Theory Methods*. DOI: 10.1080/03610928908830127

[7] Rocchetti M. (2026) Unlocking the stochastic parrot: Epistemic obligation and the decline of biological plausibility in clinical reality. *Inform. Med. Unlocked*. 62:101752. DOI: 10.1016/j.imu.2026.101752.

[8] Rocchetti M. (2026) Before the algorithm: An exemplar case of the necessity of statistical testing for epidemiological consistency in public health data. *AIMS. Public. Health*. 13(1):121-134. DOI: 10.3934/publichealth.2026008.

Figure 1: 95.6% Survival Ovelap between reproductive stories. Comparison of the local approximations of survival distributions for nulliparous women (Delta shift) and women with 2+ children. Despite statistical significance in large samples ($n=5,012$), the standardized effect size is negligible ($d=0.11$). Abbreviations: OVL: Overlapping Coefficient (%)